

YouCount
Youth Citizen Science

D6.3

IPR Plan

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D6.3 IPR plan

This plan outlines how the IP assets and IPR will be handled in the project.

The vision of YouCount are twofold, addressing and combining both the scientific and societal needs of our time. The scientific *vision* of YouCount is to strengthen the transformative and participatory aspects of CS and social science, by enabling citizen participation in all facets, reaching out for a more egalitarian way of conducting science. The societal vision of YouCount is to contribute to create inclusive and innovative societies for European youths and to empower them in promoting active citizenship and a just and equitable future, particularly for youths with disadvantages.

Table 1: Revision history

VERSION	DATE	CREATED BY	COMMENTS
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2.0	20/04/2021	Partner 2, OsloMet	Revised structure and content after inputs and scientific review
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Table 2: Terms and Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	FULL TERM
AB	Advisory Board
CS	Citizen Science
CSS	Citizen Social Science
CMS	Content Management System
D	Deliverable
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Document of Action
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
EC-GA	European Commission - Grant Agreement
EU	European Union
GA	General Assembly
GAP	Grant Agreement Preparation
ICT	Internet Communication Technology
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
LL	Living Labs
KER	Key Exploitable Results

NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
OA	Open Access
OSc	Open Science
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SEB	Safety and Ethics Board
Y-CSS	Youth Citizen Social Science
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

YouCount is an EU project funded under H2020, the Science with and for Society programme. The overarching objective of the YouCount project is to generate new knowledge and innovations to increase the social inclusion of youth at risk of exclusion through co-creative youth citizen social science and to provide evidence of the actual outcomes of citizen science.

The YouCount project is a large project with a substantial number of participants that requires proper knowledge management and knowledge transfer throughout the project period and beyond. This intellectual property rights (IPR) plan aims to support good conduct regarding intellectual property (IP) in the project. It assesses the potential key exploitable results from the project and the need for IPR protection and describes the measures taken to secure good IP management. The IP assessments show that there are few commercial IPR issues in the project beyond potential software protection of SPOTTERON’s contributions. Yet, several IP issues concerning ownership, level of openness and future exploitations of results need to be addressed. The IPR plan thus underlines the need for continuous IP considerations during the project and post-project periods and will be updated towards the end of the project when the results are available and decisions concerning the exploitation of results and possessions are required.

1 Introduction

1.1 The YouCount project

YouCount is an EU project funded under Horizon 2020, the Science with and for Society (SwafS) programme (SwafS-27-2020 – Hands-on citizen science and frugal innovation, Research and innovation action). The project includes 11 partners across Europe, as well as an Advisory Board (AB) and a Security and Ethics Board (SEB), with members from Europe and beyond.

The overarching objective of the YouCount project is to generate new knowledge and innovations to increase the social inclusion of youth at risk of exclusion through co-creative youth citizen social science (Y-CSS) and to provide evidence of the actual outcomes of Y-CSS. The project includes four main sub-studies: 1) Development of a framework for Y-CSS (WP1), 2) Implementation of a multiple case study of Y-CSS projects in nine countries across Europe (WP2&3), 3) Mixed-methods evaluation of the outcomes and impact of the Y-CSS activities and a multi-criteria assessment of the costs and benefits of Y-CSS (WP4), and 4) Creation of social and scientific impact through widespread scaling up and continuity (WP5). YouCount will support dissemination and education in Y-CSS and synergise with other CS-related projects and initiatives. The project adheres to the principles of responsible research and innovation (RRI) and open science (OSc) and is part of the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data (ORD) Pilot. YouCount is thereby influenced by the principles of OSc and open innovations as promoted by Open Research Europe and EU Horizon Europa.

1.2 Why an IPR plan for YouCount?

Proper IP management in research and innovation projects is important for effective exploitation of the results, and it is necessary to be able to disclose the partners' or project's knowledge and ideas safely, prove ownership, prevent or discourage its unauthorised use by others, and secure profit from commercial exploitation if relevant during the project period (EC, 2020).¹ Collaborative and co-creative research and development should thus be based on clear and uniform recommendations and practices that ensure equitable and fair access to intellectual property generated for the mutual benefit of all partners (including the young citizen scientists) involved (EC, 2008).²

The YouCount project consists of four sub-studies and includes a substantial number of participants with varying mindsets and interests collaborating across Europe and beyond. OSc also accentuates the need for finding an appropriate balance between open access and securing the necessary confidentiality and protection of results. These traits underline the need for proper knowledge management and knowledge transfer. A good IP strategy should therefore be an

integral part of the overall project management and its activities throughout the project period and beyond.

This IPR plan aims to translate good conduct regarding intellectual property practices into the YouCount setting. It will secure efficient IP management, support knowledge transfer activities and ensure that the consortium partners in YouCount can freely and safely disseminate and exploit the project results without infringing the IPR of the others. The document is part of YouCount Work Package 6: Project Management and Ethics (WP6). It serves as a reference document for all partners, including individuals joining the project at a later stage.

The IPR plan is based on the formal requirements and procedures for intellectual property management as set out in the EC Grant Agreement (EC-GA) 23a.1 and Consortium Agreement (CA) signed by all partners.

YouCount's IPR plan will be integrated into the Data Management Plan (DMP, D. 6.2) by July 2021 and effective exploitation of the project's results will be carried out as outlined in the continuous updated dissemination, exploitation and communication (DEC) plan (D. 5.7). The DEC plan of YouCount is currently in progress, and a first version will be completed by 31 May 2021.

Since the IPR plan comes at the beginning of the project, preceding research results, this deliverable will serve as a living document that will be updated during the project period together with the DEC plan when the key exploitable results are available and ready to be exploited and shared.

1.3 Structure of the IPR plan

The IPR plan is based on literature reviews and desktop searches. The resources provided by the H2020 Manual and European IP Helpdesk³ are also used actively in the report.

The following report consists of three main chapters: 2. Definitions; 3. Key Exploitable Results (Foreground) in YouCount; and 4. IP/IPR Management Strategies and Procedures. Each chapter is inspired by the three phases of IP management in EU projects: the proposal/starting phase, the implementation phase and the concluding phase.⁴

2 Definitions⁵

Access Rights: For the purposes of Horizon 2020, access rights are rights to use the project's results or background.

Authorship: The quality or state of being a creator (natural person) of a work. In order to be considered an author, it is generally acknowledged that a certain level of creative contribution to a work must be met. Authorship entails certain moral rights, such as the right to attribution (i.e. to be named as the author), which cannot be transferred or licensed, and therefore will stay with the author even in a situation where he/she does not own the copyright.

Background: Any data, know-how or information, whatever its form or nature, tangible or intangible, including any rights, such as intellectual property rights, which are held by participants prior to their accession to the action, needed for carrying out the action or for exploiting the results of the action, and identified by the participants.

Database: In the EU, a 'database' consists of a collection of independent works, data or other materials arranged in a systematic or methodical way and individually accessible by electronic or other means.

Domain Names: The human-friendly forms of internet addresses that are commonly used to find web sites.⁶

Foreground/Results: The concept of 'foreground' was used in the FP7 but is, for the purposes of H2020, replaced by the word 'results', which includes the information, materials and knowledge generated in a given project, whether or not they can be protected. Foreground includes the tangible and intangible results of the project. It includes IPR, similar forms of protection and unprotected know-how. Results generated outside a project do not constitute foreground.⁷

(Foreground) Results Classification (IPR Options): According to the know-how resulting from each partner, a selection of the most adequate IPR protection tools has been considered/suggested to guarantee future exploitation and IPR.⁸

Innovation Action: In Horizon 2020, innovative action refers to an action primarily consisting of activities directly aimed at producing plans and arrangements or designs for new, altered or improved products, processes or services. For this purpose, they may include prototyping, testing, demonstrating, piloting, large-scale product validation and market replication.

Open Access: Within the context of EU-funded projects, open access refers to the practice of providing online access to scientific information that is free of charge to the end-user and is reusable. In the context of research and innovation, scientific information can refer to (i) peer-reviewed scientific research articles (published in scholarly journals) or (ii) research data (data underlying publications, curated data and/or raw data).⁹

Open Data: Open data is data that can be freely used, re-used and redistributed by anyone, subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and share alike.¹⁰

Intellectual Property (IP): Creations of the mind, such as inventions, literary and artistic works, designs, and symbols, names, and images used in commerce.

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR): Private legal rights that protect creations of the human mind (IP). They are commonly divided into two categories: industrial property rights (e.g. patents, trademarks, industrial designs, geographical indications) and copyright and related rights (e.g. rights of the authors/creators and those of performing artists in their performances, producers of phonograms in their recordings, and those of broadcasters in their radio and television programmes).¹¹

Yet, the IPR plan of YouCount will apply a broad perspective on intellectual property as ‘an idea, invention, or process that derives from the work of the mind or intellect’ and where proper conduct regarding IP includes moral, social and legal aspects. These broader perspectives are important for understanding IP-related issues in social science research and innovation (where knowledge and know-how are often more intangible, fluid and processual than, e.g., technology) to achieve the best knowledge transfer and exploitation strategies for publicly funded research and to create a safe working environment for participants. Moreover, IPR-related issues in YouCount will include all phases throughout the project’s life (pre-project, project implementation and post-project). This is illustrated in Figure 1.¹²

Figure 1: IPR Management Overview

3 Key Exploitable Results (Foreground)

One important part of the IPR plan is to identify key exploitable results (KER).

The KER in YouCount are yet to be developed but will be selected and prioritised based on the criteria of a) degree of innovation, b) exploitability and c) impact. Currently, the Document of Action (Annex 1, 2.2 in the EC-GA) describes the anticipated knowledge development in YouCount that goes beyond state-of-the art. These research ambitions, illustrated in Table 3.1, point to YouCount’s innovative nature and give some indications of possible results for further exploitation and the need for assessments of IPR options that should be followed up in the updated IPR and DEC plans.

Key contributors in the project included in the IPR plan are consortium partners, including a linked third party (FD), young citizen scientists, stakeholders participating in local living labs, AB and SEB members, and EU/EC.

Table 3: Identified Key Exploitable Results in YouCount, April 2021¹³

Knowledge development and innovations	Description of IP-related project outputs	Dissemination/ exploitation of project outputs	Classification	IPR options/ protection recommended ¹⁴
Theoretical and scientific innovations (WPs 1–5)	Developing CS in the social sciences (citizen social science) and co-creative youth citizen social science Development of new knowledge and ‘know-how’ about designing and setting up Y-CSS in practice	EU deliverables Scientific publications Presentations Educational materials (handbook and toolkits) Presentations Policy briefs Use for further research	Open access Open data Publications in line with dissemination procedures (GA/CA)	GA/CA: Define/agree on ownership of results and dissemination procedures Authors’ rights, authorship citation <i>IPR options:</i> OA licenses
Methodological innovations	Designing of hands-on Y-CSS projects	EU deliverables	See above	GA/CA: Define/agree on ownership of

<p>(WPs 1, 2, 3 and 4)</p>	<p>and data collection instruments</p> <p>Evaluation framework and methodology for evaluation (Y-CSS)</p> <p>Extensions and new functionalities for software and applications of the SPOTTERON (SME) Citizen Science Platform</p>	<p>Scientific publications</p> <p>Presentations</p> <p>Educational materials (handbook and toolkits)</p> <p>New functionalities will be made available to other projects on the SPOTTERON CS Platform without extra development costs</p> <p>Use for further research</p>	<p>SPOTTERON (Cf. CA, Background): Part as functionalities in the project's applications, provided as Software as a Service (SaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), ICT services, software development and design</p> <p>Software/Applications: provided as Software as a Service (SaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), ICT services</p> <p>Designs: provided as part of software/applications or as graphic design elements/media</p> <p>Project website: provided via webhosting under an internet domain and as service</p>	<p>results and dissemination procedures</p> <p>Authors' rights, authorship citation, linking to website or tagging social media</p> <p><i>IPR options:</i> Software/design and ICT services: protected by IPR</p> <p>SaaS/PaaS</p>
<p>Social science knowledge of social inclusion</p> <p>(WPs 2, 3, 4)</p>	<p>New knowledge of positive drivers of social inclusion based on youths' own perspectives</p>	<p>EU deliverables</p> <p>Scientific publications</p> <p>Presentations</p> <p>Policy briefs</p> <p>Use for further research</p>	<p>See above</p>	<p>GA/CA: Define/agree on ownership of results and dissemination procedures</p> <p>Authors' rights, authorship citation</p> <p><i>IPR options:</i> OA licenses</p>
<p>YouCount Database</p> <p>(WPs 1–4)</p>	<p>Empirical data (raw and processed data) from each case country and</p>	<p>EU deliverables</p> <p>Scientific publications</p> <p>Presentations</p>	<p>Confidential personal data</p>	<p>GA/CA: Define/agree on ownership of data, results and</p>

	<p>cross-case analysis</p> <p>Reviews /desk research</p>	<p>Data (raw and processed/reports)</p> <p>Use for further research</p>	<p>Open data (homepage, app & OA data repository)</p> <p>Dissemination agreement (cf. GA/CA)</p> <p>Authorship citation</p>	<p>dissemination procedures.</p> <p>Data treatment agreements</p> <p>Decisions reopen data and protection needs</p> <p>Define/agree on (transfer) ownership post-project</p> <p><i>IPR options:</i> Password-protected Database rights OSc/OA licenses Specific ownership agreements</p>
<p>Development and social innovations and policymaking (WPs 1–4)</p>	<p>Co-creation of social innovations and policymaking in local living labs with stakeholders</p> <p>Policy- and SDG-related results</p>	<p>EU deliverables</p> <p>Scientific publications</p> <p>Policy briefs</p> <p>Educational materials (handbook and tool kits)</p> <p>Use for further research</p> <p>Horizon Results Platform</p>	<p>See above</p> <p>Open access and confidential personal data</p>	<p>GA/CA: Define/agree on ownership of results and dissemination procedures</p> <p>Disclosure and exploitation of results based on informed consent and local agreements with participating stakeholder LLs</p> <p><i>IPR options:</i> Confidentiality agreements, copyright, OA copyright and licenses</p>

<p>YouCount platform 1</p>	<p>Internal Teams Platform</p> <p>Internal project documents and internal exchanges provided by all participants</p>	<p>Be described in presentations and publications</p> <p>Use for further research</p>	<p>Platform only open for project partners and invited Teams Members</p> <p>Open access with respect to dissemination</p>	<p>GA/CA: Define/agree on ownership</p> <p><i>IPR options:</i> Not relevant</p>
<p>YouCount platform 2</p>	<p>Citizen science applications for smartphones and web application for browser based on the SPOTTERON Citizen Science platform</p> <p>CMS Project website based on the SPOTTERON framework for project websites</p> <p>Youth citizen science stakeholder community (list of stakeholders)</p>	<p>Use for further research</p> <p>Continuing the stakeholder community for Y-CSS in other settings and for future projects/proposal</p> <p>New functionalities will be made available to other projects on the SPOTTERON CS Platform without extra development costs</p> <p>Dissemination via online availability, news posts, social media, word-of-mouth, press coverage</p> <p>Exploitation of results via marketing activities, reference and word-of-mouth marketing in target group; strengthening</p>	<p>IPR Background SPOTTERON platform</p> <p>software/applications: provided as Software as a Service (SaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), ICT services</p> <p>Designs provided as part of software/applications or as graphic design elements/media</p> <p>Project website provided via webhosting under an internet domain and as service</p> <p>Open access to content (except user account data for SPOTTERON)</p>	<p>GA/CA: Define/agree on ownership and use during/post project</p> <p>Agree re: maintenance/ functionality of the platform post-project</p> <p><i>IPR options:ⁱ</i> software/design and ICT services: protected by IPR; provision of services and software based on SPOTTERON</p> <p>Terms of service; usage rights granted for IP-protected unique creative works (e.g. created marketing material, brand</p>

ⁱⁱ Note: Unique creative works are always and automatically protected by intellectual property rights. In Europe, we do not use the US copyright system. Creators of unique creative works cannot give away IP ownership, only grant usage rights to others.

	Content home page	of SPOTTERON platform by enriched feature-set, made available to other CS projects. Option for follow-up projects		design, online media, presentations, posters, etc.) to the YouCount project and consortium members on an unlimited basis
Project identity	Acronym, logo, templates and social media domains	Used as tools for promoting 'youth citizen social science' in further research	IPR Background SPOTTERON Open for use of consortium partners	GA/CA: Define/agree on use post-project <i>IPR options:</i> Brand design and visual project identity is protected by IPR as unique creative works; unlimited usage rights for the project identity are granted by the author(s) to the project and consortium members

In sum, the IP-related knowledge development and assets of YouCount are mostly publicly funded research and public social innovation and policymaking, except for the software innovations of SPOTTERON. The social innovations to be developed in the project will be in early development and are not expected to be prototyped or launched in the market. Most of the social science research results (except from confidential personal data) will also take shape as open access. This means that the results generated by YouCount, to a small extent, will need specific IPR measures in terms of industrial property rights (e.g. patents, trademarks, design protection, geographical indications) or copyright and related rights, except for author rights and OA licenses. This also partly applies to SPOTTERON when it comes to authorship citations beyond the IPR rights they bring into the project as an SME and brand and limitations as set out in the CA.

However, the exploitation potential of the project results and the need for IPR are still uncertain and must therefore be identified and managed throughout the whole project period. The need for additional IP protection for SPOTTERON must be carefully assessed when the commercial

exploitation opportunities for the software results are better known. Above, Table 3 (second column) identifies some key results that should be followed closely to identify and mitigate IPR risks at an early stage. The last column on the right displays specific needs for future IPR deliberations with respect to ICT developments, project identity materials and homepage, as well as the need to consider IP measures with respect to young citizen scientists and stakeholders that participate in the living labs as part of the multiple case study (WP2). Finally, ownership, database rights and future utilisation and maintenance of the YouCount platforms (especially the project home page) in the post-project period must be considered and decided upon in a later phase of the project.

4 IP/IPR Management Strategies and Procedures

As mentioned, it is still too early to design a concrete and detailed IP strategy while the project results are still under development. However, we have outlined some core strategies to be included in the IP management and procedures for further development and detailing.

4.1 Knowledge and commitment to the procedures set out in the GA and CA

The IP/IPR strategy will adhere to the IPR regulations and provisions amended for Horizon 2020 and EC-GA Section 3. We will also, according to the EC-GA 27.1, seek expert advice to help decide whether and how to protect results.

In the Grant Agreement Preparation (GAP), the consortium members have discussed IPR-related issues thoroughly as part of the signed CA that includes the main requirements in relation to IPR set out in the EU-GA (including access rights and settlement of disputes).

4.2 Creating IP awareness in the consortium

The CA has contributed to developing a common understanding and commitment to the IP/IPR requirements in the project.

In addition, the YouCount project will emphasise a working culture wherein awareness and respect of other partners' IP and ownership are part of good research conduct – for example, in relation to authorship, reference style and dissemination (see also D. 6.1 Project Executive Handbook). This is important, since IP-related conflicts have a devastating effect on trust and safe knowledge exchange as well as contributing to create a poor working milieu for researchers and others involved in scientific activities.

4.3 Background

Issues of background- and foreground-related IPRs have been clarified between the partners during the GAP/CA process.

In YouCount, nine partners have stated that, ‘to the best of their knowledge, no data, know-how or information of (partner institution) shall be needed by another party for implementation of the project (Article 25.2 Grant Agreement) or exploitation of that other party’s Results (Article 25.3 Grant Agreement).’

The partners UCLan, with their previous projects, and SPOTTERON, as a software company, have brought their know-how as background. The detailed information has been provided in the CA (p. 37). For the purpose of convenience, the descriptions of the background and specific limitations and/or conditions for implementation and exploitation are shown in Table 4.1 below.

Table 4: Background description in the CA

Partner Institution	Describe Background	Specific limitations and/or conditions for implementation (Article 25.2 Grant Agreement)	Specific limitations and/or conditions for exploitation (Article 25.3 Grant Agreement)
UCLan	University of Central Lancashire’s Centre for Citizenship and Communities’ ‘Connected Communities’ approach, using community-based, participatory research methods with social network theory and our Connected Communities theory of change: Understand, Involve, Connect. Also using the wealth of experience in using participatory and empowering approaches with young people in the Centre for Children and Young People’s Participation	None	To be agreed upon in any such event
SPOTTERON	a) Functional Extensions to the SPOTTERON Citizen Science Platform / Smartphone Apps of the Project	Developed special functionalities and extensions are part of the SPOTTERON SaaS	Access to collected data in the digital tools is provided via web interfaces, protected by login, to download the

	b) Project Identity Materials and Promotion Materials c) Website Content Management System	(Software As a Service) Platform. Access to the functionalities in the front-end is provided on a project basis in the digital toolkit of the project (e.g. in smartphone apps and interactive web apps) and via access to the data administration interface, protected by login for partners, to manage the collected data and moderate the project’s community comments and data spots	dataset of citizen science participation. Elements of the project identity (logo, font) and promotion material, e.g. image teasers, if part of the WP, will be provided via download. Access to the content management interface of the website is provided for partners participating in creating content (via login)
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4.4 Ownership and transfer of ownership of results

The YouCount project will comply with the basic rules to allocate the ownership of the project results as set out in Article 26 in the EC-GA and in Section 8 in the CA, which have been signed by all the participating partners.

These apply as follows:

- General rule: Partner who generates the project results shall have ownership.
- Joint ownership: In the case that the results are co-generated by multiple partners and it is impossible to establish the respective contribution of each partner or separate the results for the applications and for obtaining or maintaining protection, those partners who have participated in generating the results shall have joint ownership and a separate written agreement shall be signed to decide the allocation and terms of exercising ownership and all relevant issues.

The ownership for the linked third party is defined in the CA.

4.5 Dissemination policy

YouCount will adhere to the guidelines and procedures for authorship as stated in the Vancouver and NESH guidelines (see D.6.1. Project Executive Handbook) and authorship/dissemination procedures in Section 8 of the CA.

Further, YouCount will adhere to the obligations of EC-GA 29.1 to ‘disseminate’ its project results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means, including in scientific publications (in any medium), as well as exploit and provide open access to research data and publications.

At the same time, the requirements of dissemination and exploitation do not change the EC-GA obligations of YouCount partners laid out in Article 27.1 to protect results (if the results can reasonably be expected to be commercially or industrially exploited and protecting them is possible, reasonable and justified given the circumstances), as well as the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 and the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all of which still apply.

Figure 2: Balancing dissemination, open access and needs for protection and confidentiality¹⁵

Aligning with EC-GA, YouCount will thus seek to examine the possibility of legitimately protecting its results and must adequately protect them – for an appropriate period and with appropriate territorial coverage – if:

- a) the results can reasonably be expected to be commercially or industrially exploited, and
- b) protecting them is possible, reasonable and justified (given the circumstances).

The partners of YouCount will thus seek to disseminate the results as swiftly as possible, but this will only be done after all the other partners have been informed about the intention to disseminate and the content and have been given a reasonable time frame in which they can object to (elements of) the intended dissemination. This process will be supported by YouCount's Project Executive Handbook and internal Teams platform.

In addition, YouCount partners will balance the ambitions of open access and the need for securing protection and confidentiality through the following main strategies and measures (see also the upcoming D. 6.3 DMP, D.6.6. Report on recruitment strategies and consent procedures and D. POPD Requirement No.2, b July 2021):

- Protecting confidential personal data by storing it on secure servers at the participating university institutions with restricted access, while at the same time considering and choosing samples of data that are prepared and suitable for dissemination in an open data repository for research data and publications (to be decided later) linked to Open Aire and according to the FAIR principles.
- Providing open data from young citizen scientists (YCSs) at the SPOTTERON CS Platform (app), while at the same time developing features for disclosed personal data and secure GDPR.
- Attending to the legitimate IPR for SPOTTERON as a SME, while at the same time publishing new features on the platform for free and open publication of results from the development process during the project period; securing continuous considerations of whether there are results from software development that will need IPR and protection from dissemination due to their novel innovative and commercial value.

Finally, the aforementioned DEC plan, together with the CA and the IPR plan, will function as central documents, stating the rights and obligations of all beneficiaries for dissemination of project results and data, ownership of results, protection of the results and access rights.

4.6 IP risks

For the consortium partners to exploit the project results freely and successfully after the end of the project, it is essential to analyse potential risks that may influence the freedom to operate with those results. Currently, no potential risks nor conflicts have been identified among the background IP owners and the partners who are responsible for the exploitation of the results.

Yet, in order to identify and mitigate IP issues that might arise during the research and innovations processes in an early state, YouCount will regularly collect information from partners by using an IP note template provided by Europa Media (see Appendix 1). This template will be sent to all partners at all reporting periods (including internal reporting months 9 and 27). Inputs from partners will then be systematised and identified IP issues followed up on by the PC, together with the Executive Board (EB) and GA.

5 Conclusion

This IPR plan displays the potential key exploitable results from the YouCount project, assesses the need for IP protection and describes the measures taken to secure good IP management in the project. As described, there are few commercial IPR issues in the project outside the potential software protection of SPOTTERON. However, the IPR plan points to the need for continuous IP considerations during the project and post-project periods. The IPR plan will therefore be updated towards the end of the project when the results are known and decisions concerning the post-project exploitation of results and project platforms are required.

REFERENCE LIST

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- ¹ See Your Guide to IP in Horizon 2020 (kowi.de)
- ² EC: Commission Recommendation Cf. 1329 of 10.4.2008 on the management of intellectual property in knowledge transfer activities and the Code of Practice for universities and other public research institutions attached to this recommendation. (2008), European Commission
- ³ https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/regional-helpdesks/european-ip-helpdesk_en
- ⁴ EC: European IP Helpdesk. Your Guide to IP in Horizon 2020. (2020), European Commission
- ⁵ European IP Helpdesk (Europe - Glossary (europa.eu) and EC-GA.
- ⁶ World Intellectual Property Organization: WIPO IPR Handbook. (2004), WIPO
- ⁷ FLOTANT: Deliverable 8.3 – IPR Management Plan, 30/09/19. (2019)
- ⁸ CT-BIOCHAIN: Deliverable 7.5., Report of IPR Management Activities 28/05/2020. <https://ictbiochain.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Deliverable-7.5-Report-of-the-IPR-management-activities.pdf> (2020)
- ⁹ EC: H2020 Programme Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020. Version 3.2.(2017), European Commission.
- ¹⁰ Open Knowledge Foundation: Open Data Handbook. What is Open Data? (opendatahandbook.org)
- ¹¹ The World Intellectual Property Organization (2004) Intellectual Property Handbook. WIPO Publications No. 489. WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook
- ¹² FLOTANT: Deliverable 8.3 IPR Management Plan, p. 9. 190930-FLT-WP8-D8.3-V1.pdf (flotantproject.eu) (2019)
- ¹³ CT-BIOCHAIN: Deliverable 7.5., Report of IPR Management Activities 28/05/2020. (2020),
- ¹⁴ European IP Helpdesk EU-IPR-Guide-IP-in-Europe-EN (1).pdf
- ¹⁵ H2020 Manual: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/open-access_en.htm

Appendixes

Table 5: Appendixes

APPENDIX	SUBJECT	PAGE
Appendix A	IP Note Template	22

IP Note Template ²

RESULT – INTELLECUAL PROPERTY NOTIFICATIONS (IP NOTE)		
Notified by:	Date:	Work Package:
Title:		
Summary of the result achieved:		
<i>Partners who developed the result and % of input (if relevant): e.g. based on number of hours/PMs spent on the deliverable</i>		
Exploitation potential – IPR issues linked:		
Received by:	Date:	
Reviewed by the Coordinator and the EB – Conclusions:		
Action to be taken:		
Result:		

² Based on template from Europa Media

PARTNERS:

